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Interdisciplinary Practices in Management

Demonitization and its Impact on Adoption
of Digital Marketing in India

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ABSTRACT

In the emerging world of technology, digital marketing changed the whole scenario of Indian market. Demonitization, a historic event for the Indian economy, impacted almost every sector including digital marketing. Digital marketing is also known as Internet marketing, web marketing, online marketing, or e-marketing. As the name states, it is the advertising of products or services over the Internet. However, it also implies marketing through the wireless media and through e-mail. Electronic Customer Relationship Management (E-CRM) systems are also categorized under digital marketing. It can be creative, also technical through its design, development, advertising & sales over the Internet.

Through the demonitization digital payment changed the buying behavior of Indian society and prevents black money market. It helps the government to maintain a record of all transaction. People have no other option for transaction so Indian society move slowly from cash to digital transaction system. In this 21st century maximum of the companies are crooked with innovative ideas, opportunities & challenges inside the digital era. This study explores the advantages of adaption of digital marketing after demonitization and also government was aiming at transparent, corruption free, easy advertisement, less waste of time to reach customers, cashless transaction oriented economy. This study also focused on finding out the effectiveness of demonitization & adaptation of digitalization, satisfaction levels of people towards digitalization and challenges faced using digitalization after demonitization & digital marketing impact on the modern era of Indian market.

KEYWORDS: demonitization, Internet/digitalization, Technology, advertising

INTRODUCTION

Digital marketing is the marketing of products or services using digital technologies, mainly on the internet, but also including mobile phones, display advertising, and any other digital medium. In the past ten years, the Internet population varied a lot (Sandelands, 1997); an estimation of about 50 percent increase of the World Wide Web (WWW) per month and the numbers of websites double every 53 days (Gilbert, Perry and Widijoso, 1999). A 60 percent of large companies and 30 percent of midsize companies were estimated to make use of the Internet for digital marketing purposes by the year 2000 (Crain, 1994). In 2003, the first generation of internet users was fresh graduates – fast to get the concepts of online commerce and shopping.

The WWW is an electronic technology which is an effective means for marketing hotels and it also develops customer relationship in the long-run (Gilbert, Perry and Widijoso, 1999). The Internet allows firms to open a Web site in an electronic mall, have their products available to millions of

potential customers and only in a short time period. GE, IBM, Ford, Kraft, and Proctor & Gamble were the first to register "domain names" (Herbig and Hale, 1997).

Because Internet grew in only five years (Lagrosen, 2005) and there are no barriers for time or location, internet marketing has become the new era in E-commerce with petty variable cost per customer (Deighton, 1997). Marketers use full colour advertising that appeal similar to both -young and old- to attract people all over the world. The Internet is now considered as a much greater resource than traditional means of marketing (Herbig and Hale, 1997).

The role of digital India was cashless, faceless, paperless. The government's main objectives of note ban is, to eradicate counterfeit currency, resist tax evasion, destroy the black money, and terrorist financing activities, and to encourage the country towards the cashless economy. Among the unending intense argument on the benefits of

demonetization, there's been a strong growth in digital payments and transactions in the months since the currency swap was announced on November 8, according to Reserve Bank of India data. Digital transactions have increased and magnified in volume and value across various modes from wallets to cards

Debit card transactions rose to more than 1 billion in January from 817 million last year. While ATM transactions have remained constant at around 700 million, the incremental growth has been driven mostly by card swipes at PoS terminals.

The switch to the digital economy has many benefits but the question remains, does the common man of India ready to accept the move from cash to cashless transactions, yet it is a biggest question mark. Therefore, this new move will definitely have a huge impact on the digital marketing in India. It encourages people to be involved in fewer cash transactions and to use the electronic or plastic money. Apart from the most obvious boosts in terms of tax income, financial analysts, this move will have many benefits in the Indian economy. Indians are traditionally inclined to use cash transactions and therefore some may feel forced to object the transition into a cashless economy.

OBJECTIVES:

1. To study the factors influencing the customers towards digital marketing
2. To compare traditional marketing and today's marketing.
3. To identify Various Promotional Factors Adopted by Indian citizens to encourage digital marketing
4. To examine the impact and challenges faced using digitalization in post demonetization period.

Comparison study:

1. Traditional Marketing
2. Marketing Today

WHY DIGITAL MARKETING?

Some of the reasons why digital marketing is very important for your business success.

- Increase product awareness. Consumers will only buy products they know about. ...
- Reach out to a wider and bigger audience. ... (Local or Global) & Cost effectiveness. ...
- Consumer preference. ... & Increase traffic. ...
- Accessible to consumers. ..., Increase sales & Applies to companies of all

HOW TO USE IM?

- To get desired job
- To build business
- To be successful

STATISTICAL DATA:

The key facet of demonetization is that it has forced people to come online. Number of internet users has increased in both rural and urban areas. The number of internet users, which stood at around 370 million last years, has crossed 460 million by today, and this hefty growth of more than 24% has definitely increased the quantum of audience for digital ads, and thereby bringing a rich profusion of focus on digital marketing.

Impact of Demonetization on Digital Marketing

Another important fact is that rural penetration of internet users is surging which means that audience base is not only improving in numbers, but the enlarged audience base also has newer characteristics, demands and behavior.

- Rural internet penetration has grown from 18% last December to 20.26% in December 2017. The number of internet users in India is expected to reach 500 million by June 2018, said a report by the Internet and Mobile Association of India (IAMAI) and Kantar IMRB on Tuesday. Feb 20, 2018
- This statistic presents the digital population worldwide as of October 2018. As of the measured period, almost 4.2 billion people were active internet users and 3.4 billion were social media users according to global digital population.

The four P's -Product, Price, Place and Promotion have long been associated with marketing, but things have changed on the Internet/digitalization. Extra three new P's which are relevant to the digital marketer: Presentation, Processes and Personalization.

ROLE OF 7 P'S OF DIGITAL MARKETING IN THIS MODERN ERA:

1. **Product:** Product on the Internet usually changes form online, and the user experiences it electronically, in the form of text, images and multimedia. Physical goods are usually presented in the form of a detailed online catalogue that the customer can browse through. Technology allows the user to virtually touch and feel the product on the Internet -rotate it, zoom in or zoom out and even visualize the product in different configurations and combination.
2. **Price:** Price has been drastically changed over the Internet. It lets the buyer decides the price. Also it gives the buyers information about multiple sellers selling the same product. It leads to best possible deal for the buyers in terms of price. Pricing is dynamic over the Internet.
3. **Place:** Place revolves around setting up of a marketing channel to reach the customer. Internet serves as a direct marketing channel that allows the producer to reach the customer directly. The elimination of the

intermediate channel allows the producer to pass the reduced distribution cost to the customer in the form of discounts

4. **Promotion:** Promotion is extremely necessary to entice the customer to its website, as there are currently more than one billion web pages. Promoting a website includes both online and offline strategies. Online strategies include search engine optimization, banner ads, multiple points of entry, viral marketing, strategic partnership and Affiliate marketing. Presently, the cyberspace is already cluttered with thousands of sites probably selling similar products.
5. **Presentation:** The presentation of the online business needs to have an easy to use navigation. The look and the feel of the web site should be based on corporate logos and standards. About 80% of the people read only 20% of the web page. Therefore, the web page should not be cluttered with a lot of information. Also, simple but powerful navigational aids on all web pages like search engines make it easy for customer to find their way around.
6. **Processes:** Customer supports needs to be integrated into the online web site. A sales service that will be able to answer the questions of their customers fast and in a reliable manner is necessary. To further enhance after sales service, customers must be able to find out about their order status after the sale has been made.
7. **Personalization:** Using the latest software, it is possible to customize the entire web site for every single user, without any additional costs. The mass customization allows the company to create web pages' products and services that suit the requirement of the user. A customized web page does not only include the preferred layout of the customer but also a pre selection of goods the customer may be interested in.

3 KEYS TO DM:

Internet marketing Seattle business owners should consider the various ways this tool can be used to grow their companies. Through online marketing, business owners can target potential customers at the local, national and international levels. A superb online marketing strategy can do much to boost company recognition, enhance consumer awareness and increase sales. The following tips can lead to greater online marketing success.

1. Optimize Business Website

Optimization makes a website more appealing to search engines so consumers have an easier time finding your business online. There are various ways to optimize a site to bolster its rating on search engines. Placing popular keywords within web content and building quality back links will make your site rank higher on search engines to attract the interest of your target audience.

2. Create Content that Stands Out

Today's consumers are bombarded on all sides from companies vying for their attention. In order to get the upper edge, a business has to stand out. Bold and brave web content that tackles the challenges consumers face on industry specific topics is sure to hit the mark with

your target audience and distinguish your firm as an expert in its field. Such content can be characterized by:

- **Conversation points:** Live streaming platforms such as Blab and Periscope encourage customer engagement to create a more personal customer service experience. Live streaming can also "humanize" a brand, making it more appealing to your audience. Re-sharing your video on social channels increases your online marketing potential.
- **Personalization:** Personalized content focuses on the problems of real people, offering genuine, pertinent solutions that meet their needs.
- **Visuals:** Visuals maintain audience attention, reduce boredom and minimizes bounce rate of your company's landing page.

3. Maximize Use of Social Sites

Smart business owners will find ways to integrate social media platforms such as Face book, Twitter, LinkedIn and others in their online marketing strategy. By doing a little research and experimentation, you can narrow your choice of sites to those that provide optimum marketing results.

DIGITAL MARKETING TYPES (WAYS OF PROMOTIONAL PLATFORMS)

The 2 main groups of digital marketing are **online and offline**. While offline marketing involves things like radio, television and phone advertising, online marketing has 7 major categories:

1. SEARCH ENGINE OPTIMIZATION

According to Search Engine Land, SEO stands for "search engine optimization." It is the "process of getting traffic from the free, organic, editorial or natural search results on search engines."By understanding how search engines rank websites, one can optimize a website to maximize its chances of ranking well for relevant searches. However, search engine algorithms continue to change, making it essential for online businesses to stay up-to-date with best practices to claim high rankings for relevant keywords.

2. CONTENT MARKETING

According to the Content Marketing Institute, it is "a strategic marketing approach focused on creating and distributing valuable, relevant, and consistent content to attract and retain a clearly-defined audience and, ultimately, to drive profitable customer action." Basically, content marketing is the ongoing process that focuses on communicating with your customers without always selling.

3. AFFILIATED MARKETING

Affiliate marketing is the process of earning a commission by promoting other people's (or company's) products. You find a product you like, promote it to others (usually through your blog), and earn a piece of the profit for each sale that you make.

4. SEARCH ENGINE MARKETING (SEM) & PAY-PER-CLICK

SEM (Search Engine Marketing) is the process of gaining website traffic by purchasing ads on search engines. Google AdWords is by many measures the most popular paid search platform used by search marketers, followed by Bing Ads. Beyond that, there are a number of "2nd tier PPC platforms" as well as PPC advertising options on the major social networks. Typically, SEM and PPC advertising is carried out through search engines, who charge advertisers a predetermined amount every time their ad is clicked.

5. SOCIAL MEDIA MARKETING

As an end user, many people already know a lot about social media, but their knowledge about social media marketing is typically more limited. Social media marketing is a great way for businesses to fulfill their objectives in terms of building brand equity, improving customer service, reaching new customers and collecting customer feedback. If companies can create social media content that provides value to others, they can connect with customers in a profitable way.

6. EMAIL MARKETING

Email marketing has long been a pillar for any business attempting to generate sales via the internet. It provides direct contact with clients and allows you to drive prospective customers to your website. In a few simple steps, you can provide updates, exciting news, reminders, etc. to your customers in a matter of minutes.

THE 6 ONLINE MARKETING STRATEGIES EVERY ENTREPRENEUR NEEDS

- Criteria for "need" What do I mean, you "need" these **strategies**? ...
- Personal branding. Successful businesses can generate a ton of momentum from successful entrepreneurs who lead them. ...
- Content **marketing**. ...
- Search engine optimization (SEO). ...
- Conversion optimization. ...
- Social media **marketing**. ...
- Email **marketing**.

CHALLENGES/ CONSTRAINTS ON DIGITALISATION:

1. Persuading street vendors, kirana stores and traders to transact business with existing and new modes of payments.
2. Literacy rates are low to have financial inclusion of majority of the population.
3. Unstable or absence of internet infrastructure in rural areas.
4. Lack of banking of poor and those living in remote, tribal and hilly areas.
5. Transactions are not available 24*7 and on holidays in some cases.
6. To change mindset of people for using mobile transactions.
7. To inculcate confidence in users about the reliability and security of using digital payments.
8. Low use of regular internet in rural areas
9. Low penetration of smart phones in rural areas.

MARKETING OPPORTUNITY AFTER DEMONITIZATION:

1. Opportunities aplenty for e-wallet brands
2. Retail brands reduce promotions
3. Banking firms build trust and loyalty
4. The marketing channel of brands across sectors
5. The future of digital transactions

DEMONETIZATION HAS IMPACTED DIGITAL MARKETING

1. Enlarged Viewer Base for Digital Ads
2. Digital Marketing Has Become a Necessary Part of Every Marketing Campaign
3. Changing Sentiment Regarding Digital Business
4. The New 'Payments' Model of Advertising
5. The Flip Side: Sudden Fall in Advertising Budgets

ROLE OF DIGITAL MARKETING IN MODERN MARKETING

In the rapidly expanding and ever-shifting digital age in which we live, the role of Internet marketing in modern marketing is no longer a minor one. Internet marketing is a vital part of the success of any organization. From IT support to lead generation to sales, Internet marketing is beneficial to nearly every aspect of the business.

Internet marketing, which also goes by the names of online marketing, digital marketing, web marketing, e-marketing, etc., is defined as the process of promoting brands, products, or services, over the Internet. It includes any promotional actions that are done via the Web or wireless media, including email marketing, blogging, SEO, and social media.

The worldwide reach of the Internet has made it possible for businesses to easily reach hundreds of new customers and has redefined relationships between businesses to businesses (B2B) and businesses to consumers (B2C). Through the Internet, marketers from organizations of all sizes are now able to share brands, products, and services on a global scale and can do so all the time. Through websites, blogs, and social media platforms, consumers are able to find and access information about and from an organization twenty-four seven, from wherever they are.

Due to the major role of digital marketing in modern marketing, organizations cannot afford to ignore marketing online. Because the vast majority of people spend a significant amount of time online, whether they are at work or home on a desktop computer, at school on a laptop, or waiting at the airport on a smart phone or digital device, marketing through the Internet provides organizations a more effective way to promote themselves. It also provides a more efficient way because it does not involve the costs that often come with traditional marketing. Costs that often include printing brochures, shipping out promotional mailers, and paying for billboard advertising. By cutting down on expenditures, Internet marketing allows organizations to experience higher revenue.

Internet marketing also helps organizations in achieving better global branding and in building greater awareness of the products or services that they offer. Through marketing online, organizations can more strategically reach their target audience. Having the right Internet marketing strategies is an important part in helping organizations successfully market and advertise their products and services to consumers, connect with customers, and make sales.

Traditional marketing is slowly decreasing and Modern era is more focused on selecting the products and focusing more on faster work by digitalization

BENEFITS OF DIGITAL MARKETING:

1. Convenience
2. Information
3. Fewer hassles
4. Quick adjustments to market conditions
5. Lower costs
6. Relationship building
7. Audience sizing

Disadvantages of Digital Marketing

1. Dependability on technology
2. Security, privacy issues
3. Maintenance costs due to a constantly evolving environment
4. Higher transparency of pricing and increased price competition
5. Worldwide competition through globalization

FINDINGS:

1. By the demonetization drastic changes takes place in Indian economy
2. Increased the percentage of usage of digitalization.
3. Demonetization helped to urban people for quick work.
4. Yet rural people opinions that traditional marketing is better than digital marketing because low literacy level
5. Maximum percent of the customers are satisfied with the digitalization that is why 27% increased the usage of Internet after demonetization.
6. Low internet usage in rural India.

SUGGESTIONS:

1. Government should take initiatives to give awareness about digitalization and its benefits for rural population.
2. Different payment modes need to be put in place for different category of people.
3. Removal of constraints for making India a less -cash economy.
4. Companies or banks should resolve the problems or challenges properly, so that customer will get confidence on digitalization

CONCLUSION:

The historic step brought about an upsurge in online transactions in a very short period. But on other side, as soon the cash situation became normal, many people started shifting back to traditional methods, which was a disappointment.

Internet search engines are the best information retrieval systems available. The digital payment had given relief and force to learn digital transaction after demonetization. People adopted technology slowly, but don't wanted to pay

extra for digital transaction. They bring any kind of information for internet users, from local restaurants to international news. The digitalization makes easier and possible for business and companies to do transactions with their clients and customers. Digital marketing helps to do smart work rather than hard work and as it is a paper free (i.e. go green) it is worldwide accepted. There is a great possibility to earn while working from home and also it helps to Savings on travel cost.

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